

APPLYING BLOOM'S TAXONOMY IN TEACHING EFFECTIVELY**Mekhriniso Norova**

*English teacher of school N47
Narpay District, Samarkand region*

Nargiza Alimardanova

*English teacher of school N6
Payarik District, Samarkand region*

Zilola Rasulova

*English teacher of school N6
Payarik District, Samarkand region*

Annotation: *Bloom's taxonomy was initially meant to be a technique of measuring competency by classifying a student's knowledge into one of six levels, which are frequently physically displayed as a pyramid. Each step of the pyramid, from bottom to top, represents a movement from a lower order thinking skill to a higher order one; from fundamental tangible cognition to a more abstract, conceptual understanding.*

Keywords: *Bloom's taxonomy, evaluation, learning approach, critical thinking*

The purpose of this article is to assist you in comprehending Bloom's Taxonomy and how you might use it in your own teaching and learning. If you've been teaching for any length of time, you've almost certainly come across Bloom's taxonomy at some point. Perhaps you are already extremely familiar with it and use it on a regular basis to inform your teaching and evaluation. However, for many of us, our knowledge of Bloom's taxonomy may be restricted to a casual mention of it at a teaching conference or staff training. In summary, Bloom's taxonomy provides a hierarchical model of cognitive talents and learning objectives. Bloom's taxonomy was originally intended as a method of assessing competency by categorizing a

student's knowledge into one of six levels, which are sometimes depicted visually in the shape of a pyramid. From bottom to top, each level of the pyramid indicates a transition from a lower order thinking skill to a higher order one; from basic concrete cognition to a more abstract, conceptual understanding. Benjamin Bloom is the originator of this taxonomy of educational aims. Bloom was an American educational psychologist best known for his contributions to the idea of mastery learning and this well-known and commonly used taxonomy. Bloom's Taxonomy was originally developed by educational psychologist Benjamin Bloom in 1956 and revised by researchers Lorin Anderson and David Krathwohl in 2001. It could be a show of learning that centers not on substance and instruction, but on how understudies think, and how best to advance cognition and understanding in understudies. This approach classifies, in a progressive way, the various objectives and abilities that instructors trust to assist understudies accomplish. Agreeing to Bloom, high-level cognition is subordinate on a solid establishment of lower-level aptitudes on which they are built. There are six levels in Bloom's Taxonomy:

The 6 Levels of Bloom's Taxonomy

1. The first level is to Remember.

Example activities at the Remembering level: memorize a poem, recall state capitals, and remember math formulas

2. The second level is to Understand.

Example activities at the Understanding level: organize the animal kingdom based on a given framework, illustrate the difference between a rectangle and a square, and summarize the plot of a simple story

3. The third level is to Apply.

Example activities at the Application level: use a formula to solve a problem, select a design to meet a purpose, reconstruct the passage of a new law through a given government/system

4. The fourth level is to Analyze.

Example activities at the Analysis level: identify the ‘parts of’ democracy, explain how the steps of the scientific process work together, identify why a machine isn’t working

5. The fifth level is to Evaluate.

Example activities at the Evaluation level: make a judgment regarding an ethical dilemma, interpret the significance of a given law of physics, illustrate the relative value of a technological innovation in a specific setting—a tool that helps recover topsoil farming, for example.

6. The sixth and highest level is to Create.

Bloom's taxonomy is an excellent tool for assisting teachers in developing higher order critical thinking skills in their pupils. Using the taxonomy principles throughout the planning process allows instructors to focus on suitable objectives for groups and individuals, as well as plan for their advancement in the short, medium, and long term. The taxonomy provides a clear framework or organizational structure for defining instructional goals, as well as a consistent beginning point from which to design lessons. This learning approach prioritizes thinking and understanding over the present emphasis on developing cutting-edge curriculum and data-driven student evaluation. Because Bloom's Taxonomy is built on a precise hierarchy of learning levels, each level is an essential component of achieving deeper, more advanced cognitive skills and abilities. According to TES, building on each level in your lesson plans will help pupils to think in "increasingly more complex ways." Developing various lesson plans for each level of learning can also be aided by modern techniques such as the use of technology or supporting student-led lesson planning. The first level of learning — remembering — is frequently undervalued in today's academic contexts. However, all six levels are critical to the Bloom's Spiraling process's effectiveness. According to “Teach Thought”, remembering or memorizing broadens and diversifies a student's knowledge base, expanding their capacities and providing them with material to apply at higher levels of knowledge.

For example, in language arts, begin by memorizing a poem, then move on to comprehending it, and so on, utilizing the same text across all levels of learning. Students will have the basis and ability to create creative works based on their gathered thoughts and deeper comprehension of the literary form and subject matter by the conclusion of the procedure. Educator Mike Gershon, author of "How to Use Bloom's Taxonomy in the Classroom," devised many techniques to lesson preparation based on the levels of Bloom's Taxonomy.

Divide the taxonomy into three sections: recall and comprehend, apply and analyze, and assess and develop. Then, break your lecture into three sections and apply each of the learning stages listed above. For example, in the first segment, utilize listing, summarizing, explaining to a partner, and paraphrasing to go through each level of learning. Using the "All/Most/Some" concept, you may create differentiated classes. Expected outcomes are determined by selecting the levels of learning that are most suited for your pupils. For example, "All students will recall and sketch the idea, the majority of students will grasp and summarize the topic, and some students will analyze and arrange the notion". Make a "task bank" of activities and questions for each learning level and have it handy for organizing sessions and establishing objectives. Although challenging for many students, practicing self-assessment and the concepts of critique, reconstruction, defense, assessment, and evaluation can be valuable assessment tools for both students and teachers. Using the Bloom system framework, students can self-assess through written reflection and peer discussion. After completing the assignment, students use a scoring chart or teacher-created prompts to record what they see as their strengths and weaknesses. They then compare their observations with another student, share their knowledge and answer what they have in common and how they differ. Classes have teacher-led discussions, extra parts and explanations. Self-assessment skills will help students use and understand complex concepts in the future.

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throughout the planning process allows instructors to focus on suitable objectives for groups and individuals, as well as plan for their advancement in the short, medium, and long term. The major usefulness of Bloom's taxonomy is its adaptability as a tool in a variety of domains of learning. Its broad reach provides a valuable framework for organizing and planning learning experiences that are intended to encompass a wide variety of cognitive capacities while being non-prescriptive.

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